

Ndoni Humanoid Robots Scale

NHRS

Introduction:

The **Ndoni Humanoid Robots Scale (NHRS)** is a unique way of measuring a civilization's technological advancement based on its proliferation of humanoid robots in relation to its population. Unlike the **Kardashev Scale**, which gauges a civilization's progress by the amount of energy it harnesses, the NHRS focuses on the integration of humanoid robots in everyday life.

Formula:

$$\text{NHRS} = \frac{\text{Number of Humanoid Robots}}{\text{Number of Living Persons}}$$

Civilization Types (Examples):

- **Type 1 Civilization (NHRS 1):** A civilization where there is **1 humanoid robot per living person**. This means that for every human, there is one humanoid robot available to assist, work, or perform tasks, reflecting a high degree of robotic integration.
- **Type 2.7 Civilization (NHRS 2.7):** A civilization where there are (an average) of **2.7 humanoid robots for every living person**. Such a civilization has reached an even higher level of robotic proliferation, with multiple robots supporting each human, indicating advanced automation and technology reliance.

Here is a table with the projected data for the Ndoni Humanoid Robots Scale (NHRS):

Timeframe (Year)	Human Population (Billions)	Humanoid Robots Built (Billions)	NHRS (Robots per Person)
2100	10	5	0.50
2150	12	15	1.25
2200	14	35	2.50
2250	16	64	4.00
2300	18	108	6.00

This table outlines the human population, the number of humanoid robots built, and the corresponding NHRS for each timeframe. (Note: The data in this chart are approximations).

Conclusion

This scale could serve as a benchmark for evaluating the robotic capabilities of future societies, focusing on the relationship between robotics and population dynamics.

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